

Peter de Knijff, Rick de Leeuw, and Marije te Raa.

Department of Human Genetics, Leiden University Medical Center, Leiden, The Netherlands.

Introduction

Within the Old World leaf warbler group (genus *Phylloscopus*), the Chiffchaff *Ph. collybita* s. l. species group represents 12 phenotypically very similar bird taxa with a trans-palaearctic breeding distribution [1]. A reliable field-identification of the various taxa is difficult and sometimes even impossible (but see [2]). In order to provide a better insight into the plumage variation of *Ph. collybita* s.l. taxa we embarked upon a large study (in the end encompassing ~1250 different individuals representing all currently recognised taxa: Common Chiffchaff *Ph. collybita* with subspecies *collybita*, *abietinus*, *brevirostris*, *caucasicus*, *menzbieri*, and *tristis*; Canary Islands Chiffchaff *Ph. canariensis* with subspecies *canariensis* and (the very likely extinct) *exsul*; Mountain Chiffchaff *Ph. sindianus* with subspecies *sindianus* and *lorenzii*, and the Iberian Chiffchaff *Ph. ibericus*. Most attention was paid to the occurrence and identification of *collybita*, *abietinus*, and *tristis*, all three regularly occurring on Autumn migration in north-western Europe. We sequenced, depending on the study, various parts of the mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) gene cytochrome B, the ND2 gene, and various smaller fragments of other mtDNA genes. For the purpose of a reliable phylogenetic reconstruction of the full species group we also sequenced complete mtDNA genomes. Finally, in order to study the rate of hybridisation between *abietinus* and *tristis* among migrants, we genotyped 294 reciprocally fixed SNPs. In this document we describe all laboratory procedures and subsequent biostatistical and phylogenetic analyses. We also show some of the resulting data. This document serves as supplementary information to a series of published articles.

mtDNA DNA-sequencing of Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita* ssp. feather /toepad samples

DNA-isolation from feather and toepad samples was performed using the QIAamp DNA Mini and Blood Mini kit. Feathers or toepads were put in a 2mL tube containing 400µL ATL buffer. 10µL ProtK and 3µL DTT (1M) were added. Samples were incubated at 56°C. After 2 hours incubation, samples were checked to see whether raw pieces were still visible. If so, another 10µL ProtK and 3µL DTT (1M) was added. When after 4 hours of incubation, no raw material was visible, extraction was continued. If raw material was still visible the incubation was left overnight and extraction was continued by adding 400µL AL buffer, vortexing and 10 minutes incubation at 70°C. Afterwards 400µL 100% ethanol was added. The mixture was applied to the column according to step 6 of the QIAamp DNA Mini and Blood Mini Handbook Protocol: DNA Purification from Dried Blood Spots. The extraction was completed following the remainder of the steps in this protocol except for the elution which was performed with 80µL nuclease free water with a centrifuge step of 8000rpm for 2 minutes in soft mode.

We developed a number of different mtDNA sequencing protocols: (i) One targeting a cytochrome B (CYTB) fragment of 309 basepairs (bp.); (ii) One targeting two overlapping CYTB fragment with a combined size of 945 (bp.); (iii) One targeting the full mtDNA genome, (iv) the full ND2 gene of 1041 bp., and (v) in order to distinguish with more accuracy the two highly similar taxa *brevirostris* and *caucasicus* without the need to sequence the full mtDNA genome, we developed three additional sequence protocols targeting short mtDNA fragments of ND1, ATP8/ATP6, and ND3/tRNA-ARG each of which contained SNPs specific for each of the three forementioned taxa. In order to reliably estimate the possible rate of hybridization between *abietinus* and *tristis* individuals we further developed an assay that enables genotyping by sequencing of 294 autosomal SNPs that have reciprocally fixed homozygous genotype differences in allopatric populations of *abietinus* and *tristis*.

PCR reaction targeting 309 bp. of CYTB (CytB-set1)

In order to sequence a fragment of 309 bp. of the *collybita* mitochondrial CYTB gene, a single PCR was performed with an input of 2.5-5µL of DNA-extract. See Table 1 for PCR-primer sequences. The PCR-mix contained Geneamp™ 10x PCR-buffer1 (Applied biosystems), 0.2mM dNTP's (GE healthcare),

0.4pmol per primer (Table 1) and 2U AmpliTaq gold DNA polymerase (Applied biosystems) in a total volume of 50µL. PCR's were run on a GeneAmp® PCR System 9700 with the following program. 94°C for 10 min, 36 cycles of 94°C for 30 seconds, 50°C for 30 seconds and 72°C for 2 minutes ending with 72°C for 10 minutes.

PCR reactions targeting 945 bp. of CYTB (CytB-frag2 and CytB-frag3)

In order to sequence a fragment of 945 bp. of the *collybita* mitochondrial CYTB gene, two overlapping PCR's were performed with an input of 2.5-5µL of DNA-extract. See Table 1 for PCR-primer sequences. The PCR-mix contained Geneamp™ 10x PCR-buffer1 (Applied biosystems), 0.2mM dNTP's (GE healthcare), 0.4pmol per primer (Table 1) and 2U AmpliTaq gold DNA polymerase (Applied biosystems) in a total volume of 50µL. PCR's were run on a GeneAmp® PCR System 9700 with the following program. 94°C for 10 min, 35 cycles of 94°C for 20 seconds, 55°C for 20 seconds and 72°C for 20 seconds ending with 72°C for 10 minutes.

PCR reaction targeting 110 bp. of ND1 (Brevi-set1)

In order to sequence a fragment of 110 bp. of the *collybita* mitochondrial ND1 gene, a single PCR was performed with an input of 2.5-5µL of DNA-extract. See Table 1 for PCR-primer sequences. The PCR-mix contained Geneamp™ 10x PCR-buffer1 (Applied biosystems), 0.2mM dNTP's (GE healthcare), 0.4pmol per primer (Table 1) and 2U AmpliTaq gold DNA polymerase (Applied biosystems) in a total volume of 50µL. PCR's were run on a GeneAmp® PCR System 9700 with the following program. 94°C for 10 min, 36 cycles of 94°C for 30 seconds, 50°C for 30 seconds and 72°C for 2 minutes ending with 72°C for 10 minutes.

PCR reaction targeting 125 bp of ND3 gene/trNA-ARG (Brevi-set2)

In order to sequence a fragment of 125 bp. of the *collybita* mitochondrial ND3 gene/trNA-ARG boundary, a single PCR was performed with an input of 2.5-5µL of DNA-extract. See Table 1 for PCR-primer sequences. The PCR-mix contained Geneamp™ 10x PCR-buffer1 (Applied biosystems), 0.2mM dNTP's (GE healthcare), 0.4pmol per primer (Table 1) and 2U AmpliTaq gold DNA polymerase (Applied biosystems) in a total volume of 50µL. PCR's were run on a GeneAmp® PCR System 9700 with the following program. 94°C for 10 min, 36 cycles of 94°C for 30 seconds, 50°C for 30 seconds and 72°C for 2 minutes ending with 72°C for 10 minutes.

PCR reaction targeting 240 bp. of ATP8/ATP (Brevi-set3)

In order to sequence a fragment of 240 bp. of the *collybita* mitochondrial ATP8/ATP6 genes boundaries, a single PCR was performed with an input of 2.5-5µL of DNA-extract. See Table 1 for PCR-primer sequences. The PCR-mix contained Geneamp™ 10x PCR-buffer1 (Applied biosystems), 0.2mM dNTP's (GE healthcare), 0.4pmol per primer (Table 1) and 2U AmpliTaq gold DNA polymerase (Applied biosystems) in a total volume of 50µL. PCR's were run on a GeneAmp® PCR System 9700 with the following program. 94°C for 10 min, 36 cycles of 94°C for 30 seconds, 50°C for 30 seconds and 72°C for 2 minutes ending with 72°C for 10 minutes.

PCR reactions targeting 1041 bp. of ND2 (ND2)

In order to sequence the full 1041 bp. of the *collybita* mitochondrial ND2 gene, we followed a slightly adjusted protocol based on Reeves et al. (2008). In short, PCR's were performed with an input of 2.5-5µL of DNA-extract. See Table 1 for PCR-primer sequences. The PCR-mix contained Geneamp™ 10x PCR-buffer1 (Applied biosystems), 0.2mM dNTP's (GE healthcare), 0.4pmol per primer (Table 1) and 2U AmpliTaq gold DNA polymerase (Applied biosystems) in a total volume of 50µL. PCR's were run on a GeneAmp® PCR System 9700 with the following program. 94°C for 10 min, 35 cycles of 94°C for 20 seconds, 55°C for 20 seconds and 72°C for 20 seconds ending with 72°C for 10 minutes.

PCR-product purification

The PCR-products were visualized using the QIAxcel. Afterwards a purification step using the QIAquick® PCR purification kit (QIAGEN) was performed according to the protocol from this kit. Elution was performed in 20-70µL Aquabrain depending on the amount of PCR-product visible on the Qiaxcel.

Sequencing PCR

Forward and reverse sequencing PCR's were performed using an input of 1-4µL of purified PCR-product. PCR-mix contained: 5x sequencing buffer big dye terminator V1.1 v3.1 (Life Technologies), 0.6pmol sequencing primer (see Table 2) and 2µL BigDye® Terminator v3.1 ready reaction mix (Life Technologies) in a total volume of 10µL. Sequencing PCR's were run on a pre-heated (96°C) GeneAmp® PCR System 9700 with the following program. 96°C for 1 min, 25 cycles of 96°C for 10 seconds, 50°C for 5 seconds and 60°C for 4 minutes.

Sequencing PCR purification

12µL water was added to the sequencing PCR-product. Then the product was purified using the DyeEx® 2.0 Spin kit (QIAGEN), protocol for Dye-Terminator Removal.

Sequencing

Purified sequencing PCR-products were run on an AB3100 Genetic Analyzer or Spectrum Compact.

Table 1: Forward and reverse primer sequences for the CYTB sequencing of *phylloscopus* samples. Lowercase sequences tgtaaacgacggccagt and caggaaacagctatgacc are M13 tails.

Primer name	Primer sequence
L14841-21M13F_CB_set1	5'- tgtaaacgacggccagtCCATCCAACATCTCAGCATGATGAAA -3'
H15149-M13REV_CB_set1	5' caggaaacagctatgaccGCCCTCAGAATGATATTTGTCCTCA-3'
CytB-frag2_phylloscopus-for	5'- tgtaaacgacggccagtTCATAGCCAATGCTTCGTC-3'
CytB-frag2_phylloscopus-rev	5'- caggaaacagctatgaccGCGTGAAGTTTTCTGGGTCT-3'
CytB-frag3_phylloscopus-for	5'- tgtaaacgacggccagtATCCTCCTTGCTCCCTAGC-3'
CytB-frag3_phylloscopus-rev	5'- caggaaacagctatgaccAATGGATACGAGGGGAAGA-3'
Brevi-set1-21M13f (ND1)	5'- tgtaaacgacggccagtGCCTTCCTTACACTAGTAGAACG-3'
Brevi-set1-M13rev (ND1)	5'- caggaaacagctatgaccTGGAGAAGATGATGAGGGCC-3'
Brevi-set2-21M13f (ND3)	5'- tgtaaacgacggccagtCTCCATGAGCTACCCAAC-3'
Brevi-set2-M13rev (ND3)	5'- caggaaacagctatgaccTGAGCCGAAATCAACTGTCT-3'
Brevi-set3-21M13f (ATP8)	5'- tgtaaacgacggccagtCATACTCCCTCATTATCCAACCT-3'
Brevi-set3-M13rev (ATP8)	5'- caggaaacagctatgaccGAGGGGTTATTAGTTGTTTTGTGA-3'
L5219Met (ND2)	5'- tgtaaacgacggccagtCCCATACCCGAAAATGATG-3'
H6313Trp (ND2)	5'- caggaaacagctatgacc CTCTATTTAAGGCTTTGAAGGC-3'

Table 2: Overview of the forward and reverse primer sequences for the sequencing PCR

	Forward	Reverse
Sequencing PCR primers	TGTA AACGACGGCCAGT	CAGGAAACAGCTATGACC

Full mtDNA-sequencing, genome assembly and gene annotation

DNA extracts were sheared using the Covaris S2 to an average target length of approximately 600 bp. Adapters were ligated using the Kapa Hyper Prep kit according to the manufacturer's procedures (07962371001; Roche Diagnostics). If necessary a library amplification was used to boost the library yield. Sequencing was performed using the MiSeq® Sequencer according to the manufacturer's procedures (Illumina, 600 cycles v3 chemistry). Paired-end reads were adapter trimmed by the Miseq reporter Software.

For the first Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita* sample we used two complementary approaches to obtain a reliable and full-length mtDNA genome. First we used MITObim version 1.8 with a cytB fragment of 945 bp. as seed-sequence to filter a read pool that resembles mitochondrial reads in multiple iterations rendering a draft mtDNA genome consisting of overlapping reads. Subsequently we used the raw read pool of the first Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita* and aligned these with BWA version 0.7.17 to an unpublished *Phylloscopus trochilus* reference mtDNA genome kindly provided by Prof. Dr. Staffan Bensch (Lund University, Sweden). Both draft mtDNA genomes were aligned using ClustalW (4) embedded in BioEdit 7.2.5 (5) and compared by eye for possible inconsistencies. As a last step we created a Bam file with SAMtools version 1.10 of the relevant reads. Raw reads of all subsequent Chiffchaff samples were aligned against this first Chiffchaff mtDNA genome by means of BWA v. 0.7.17 and the consensus genomes were subsequently re-aligned using BioEdit 7.2.5, and manually inspected for possible inconsistencies.

Protein coding genes (PCG), tRNAs and rRNAs were annotated by the MITOS WebServer (<http://mitos2.bioinf.uni-leipzig.de/index.py>) and blasted against the NCBI database of mitochondrial sequences. Further finetuning of the PCG sequences was done by means of the Open Reading Frame Finder portal of NCBI (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/orffinder/>). tRNA prediction by MITOS was verified by tRNAscan-SE v1.3.172. Mitochondrial maps were generated by OGDRAW (<https://chlorobox.mpimp-golm.mpg.de/OGDraw.html>).

Autosomal SNP genotyping by sequencing

Recently, Talla et al. (6) and Shipalina et al. (7) convincingly demonstrated that two Chiffchaff taxa, *Ph. c. abietinus* and *Ph. c. tristis* hybridize and that an unknown number of individuals cannot reliably attributed to either of these taxa by means of mtDNA only. Hybrid individuals were relatively easy identified by means of autosomal SNP genotypes. Especially reciprocally fixed SNPs (8) are sensitive and ideally suited to identify F1 hybrids, F2 hybrids, and lower-order backcrosses. We therefore decided to develop a single multiplex assay that would target ~300 fixed SNPs. For this we were able to use the VCF-files of 1695 SNPs that were found to be reciprocally fixed (see refs 6 and 7) between *abietinus* and *tristis*, kindly supplied by Niclas Backström (Uppsala University, Sweden), as reference sequences.

In order to genotype a high number of autosomal SNPs in low-concentration and DNA-extracts with a variable DNA fragment length we developed a new technique that allows us to sequence very short DNA fragments but also get the most out of the existing sequence length available. For this we combined two recently described techniques, Guide-seq (9), and Targeted Single Primer Enrichment (10) rendering a very sensitive genotyping-by-sequencing or sequencing protocol. The procedure that we followed here allows us to amplify target regions without a specific length requirement, using a single primer enrichment based procedure. We refined the protocol to be sensitive, specific and suited for highly degraded DNA. This has been done by introducing a new design involving additional PCR-steps and enzymatic clean-ups that do not rely on a difference in DNA-length.

We automatically designed primers for the 1659 fixed SNPs using a bash script that utilizes Primer3 and we designed two left primers using the VCF files. The Primer3 input and settings were as follows, the sequence template consisted of 200 bases downstream and 5 bases upstream the SNP positions. The target sequence was set on 2 bases downstream of the SNP and 2 bases upstream the SNP position. The primer length was minimal 15 bases and maximal 25 bases with an optimum of 20 bases. All other settings for Primer3 were default. For each primer design the top hit was collected in a complete csv file, resulting in 1695 forward primers. We obtained a final selection of 298 SNPs using a selection that was based on the distance to the SNP being as close as possible to handle degraded DNA. We also tried to distribute the final selection over the chromosomes as much as possible, simultaneously aiming for a melting temperature of about 60 degrees Celsius. With the method described below, these 294 SNPs could be genotyped by sequencing in a single multiplex reaction in a single DNA sample.

The total GUIDE-seq procedure exists of the following steps: (i) DNA extraction (for this see above), (ii) adapter ligation, (iii) first target-specific single primer enrichment PCR, (iv) second nested target-specific single primer enrichment PCR, and (v) a barcoding PCR.

Whenever needed the DNA extracts were sheared using the Covaris S2, the average target length was approximately 600 bp. Both adapters (from 9, see Table 3) were ligated using the Kapa Hyper Prep kit (07962371001, Roche Diagnostics) according to the manufacturer's procedures. An enzymatic clean-up was used to remove excess adapters. We used 0.3U Lambda Exo nuclease (M0262L, New England Biolabs) and 1.3U Exonuclease I (M0293L, New England Biolabs) in 1x Exonuclease I reaction buffer. This was followed by an 1.2x Ampure XP (Agencourt) bead clean-up according to manufacturer's protocol.

Using KAPA HIFI Uracil (07959079001, Roche Diagnostics) the targets were amplified with one target specific primer (Table 4, outer primers) for each of the selected 299 autosomal SNPs and a primer (BUP-exo, see table 3) that binds to the ligated adapter. As an PCR enhancer we used 0.05mM tetramethylammonium chloride. The thermocycling conditions were: 2 minutes at 98°C; followed by 20 seconds at 98°C, 5 minutes at 62°C, 1 minute at 72°C for 26 cycles and a hold at 4°C.

A PCR cleanup was done by incubating each reaction with USER II (M5508L, New England Biolabs) and EXOI (M0293L, New England Biolabs) for 20 min at 37°C, 5 minutes at 80°C, followed by a 1.2x Ampure XP (Agencourt) bead clean-up according to manufacturer’s protocol.

A second PCR, in order to increase specificity and target enrichment is performed with the KAPA HIFI kit (07958935001, Roche Diagnostics) using a second series of 299 SNP-specific primers (Table 5, inner primers) that bind the target within the former amplified regions. On the adapter side a primer is used that completes the ligated adapter with a sample index and P5 tail (I5-index primer, Table 3). As an PCR enhancer we used 0.05mM tetramethylammonium chloride. The thermocycling conditions were: 2 minutes at 98°C; followed by 20 seconds at 98°C, 5 minutes at 62°C, 1 minute at 72°C for 8 cycles and a hold at 4°C. After this a PCR cleanup was performed with 1.2x Ampure XP (Agencourt) beads according to manufacturer’s protocol.

A third PCR is performed with a p5-primer (table 3) and a p7 and indexing primer (Table 3) targeting the tail on the target-specific primers. Finally a PCR cleanup was performed with 0.8x Ampure XP (Agencourt) beads according to manufacturer’s protocol.

Sequencing was performed using the MiSeq® Sequencer according to the manufacturer’s procedures (Illumina, 600 cycles v3 chemistry). Paired-end reads were adapter trimmed by the Miseq reporter Software. Using a homemade pipeline that uses UNIX commands to extract the reads that match the SNP-flanking sequences. Using MUSCLE (version 3.8.31) the target sequence is aligned to the reference sequence and an identity score is calculated by dividing the total read length by the matching bases. This score is used to filter out a-specific reads. The pipeline outputs a tab delimited text file with the genotype of each SNP. With the use of Microsoft Excel the data was further formatted. Since we targeted reciprocally fixed SNPs, and were interested in inferring hybrid-status, the homozygous *abietinus* specific genotype was scored as 0. The *tristis*-specific homozygous genotype was scored as 1. Heterozygous genotypes were scored as 0.5. Summed values were averaged over all SNPs of a single individual, with the average score 0 indicating a 100% pure *abietinus* and a score of 1 indicating a 100% pure *tristis*.

Table 3. Universal (non-locus specific) GUIDE-seq primers.

Primer name	Primer sequence
adapteroligo1	/5lnvddT*/iisodG*/iisodG/* C*G*U CAG AUG UGU AUA AGA GAC AG(N1:25252525) (N1)(N1)(N1) (N1)(N1)(N1) (N1)(N1)(N1) (N1)(N1)T TCT GAG CGA TTA TAG GAG TCC T
adapteroligo2	/5Phos/GGACTCCTATGGTCGCTCAGAA
BUP-exo	CGUCAGAUGUGUAUAAGAGACAG
p5-primer	AATGATACGGCGACCAC*C*G*A
I5-index-primer	AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCTACAC-INDEX-I5-TCGTGGCAGCGTCAGATG TGTATAAGAGACAG
I7-index-primer	CAAGCAGAAGACGGCATAACGAGAT-INDEX-I7-GTGACTGGAGTTCAGACGTGTGC TCTCCGATCT

Table 4. List of locus specific GUIDE-seq primers (n=245) is attached at the end of this document.

References

1. Marova I, Ilyina I, Kvartalnov P, Grabovsky V, Belokon M, Solovyova E, Ivanitskii V. 2021. From the Bosporus to Kopet Dagh: morphological, genetic and bioacoustic variation in the Chiffchaff in Turkey, the Caucasus and western Turkmenistan. *Ardea* 2021; 109: 1 - 16.
2. Shirihi, H, Svensson L. Handbook of Western Palearctic Birds. Volume 1, 2018. Passerines: Larks to Warblers. Bloomsbury, London, UK.
3. Reeves AB, Drovetski S V., Fadeev I V. Mitochondrial DNA data imply a stepping-stone colonization of Beringia by arctic warbler *Phylloscopus borealis*. *J Avian Biol.* 2008; 39: 567–575.
4. JD Thompson, DG Higgins, TJ Gibson. CLUSTAL W: improving the sensitivity of progressive multiple sequence alignment through sequence weighting, position-specific gap penalties and weight matrix choice. *Nucleic Acids Res* 1994; 22: 4673 - 4680.
5. Hall TA. 1999. BioEdit: a user-friendly biological sequence alignment editor and analysis program for Windows 95/98/NT. *Nucl Acids Symp Ser* 1999; 41:95-98.
6. Talla V, Kalsoom F, Shipalina D, Marova I, Backström N. Heterogeneous patterns of genetic diversity and differentiation in European and Siberian Chiffchaff (*Phylloscopus collybita abietinus* / *P. tristis*). *G3* 2017; 7: 3983 – 3998.
7. Shipilina D, Serbyn M, Ivanitskii V, Marova I, Backström N. Patterns of genetic, phenotypic, and acoustic variation across a chiffchaff (*Phylloscopus collybita abietinus* / *tristis*) hybrid zone. *Ecol Evol* 2017; 7: 2169 – 2180.
8. McFarlane SE, Pemberton JM. Detecting the True Extent of Introgression during Anthropogenic Hybridization. *Trends Ecol Evol* 2019; 34: 315 – 326.
9. Tsai SQ, Zheng Z, Nguyen NT, Liebers M, Topkar VV, Thapar V, Wyvekens N, Khayter C, Lafrate AJ, Le LP, Aryee MJ, Joung JK. GUIDE-seq enables genome-wide profiling of off-target cleavage by CRISPR-Cas nucleases. *Nature biotechnology* 2015; 33: 187 – 197.
10. Peng Q, Xu C, Kim D, Lewis M, DiCarlo J, Wang Y. Targeted single primer enrichment sequencing with single end Duplex-UMI. *Scientific Reports* 2019; 9: 4810. doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-41215-z 3

Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita*; Alphen aan den Rijn, The Netherlands; 5 February 2021; © P. de Knijff

Table 4. SNP (n=294) specific GUIDEseq primers (part of Genetic research protocols for studying Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita* s.l. taxa)

Type / chromosome / position	primer sequence	Type / chromosome / position	primer sequence
Outer_Ch24-23244	GTTTAGCTGAAGTAAAAAGTTGCA	Inner_Ch24-23244	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCACCCCGTGATCCCATAA
Outer_Ch20-28102	TGGTTTTGCTTGCTCTTAAGATAGT	Inner_Ch20-28102	cgtgtgctctccgatctGTGGCAATGGAGTTGATCAGT
Outer_Ch20-28137	ACCACTAAATCATTAGCAAAGCTCT	Inner_Ch20-28137	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTCACGTGCAGAAGGGGAAA
Outer_Ch17-36550	ACAGCAGAAACATGTATTTGAGTGT	Inner_Ch17-36550	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCCCAAGGAAGAAGCTCTCC
Outer_Ch17-38142	GGCAAGAAAACCTTACTAAGAAGT	Inner_Ch17-38142	cgtgtgctctccgatctATCAACAGCAAGGGGAGGT
Outer_Ch23-47269	AAGCTCATAGGTTGTGAGACC	Inner_Ch23-47269	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCTGCGCTTGGGAAAACAAA
Outer_Ch23-47273	GGTTGTGAGACCTGCGC	Inner_Ch23-47273	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCTGCGCTTGGGAAAACAAA
Outer_Ch24-80400	TGCAGGAGCTCCCATTAATCC	Inner_Ch24-80400	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCCATGCAACCCCTACAGC
Outer_Ch24-80475	AGCAAACACAGCTCCTGAG	Inner_Ch24-80475	cgtgtgctctccgatctACACCTTCCCATCTGCTTG
Outer_Ch24-81840	TGAAAGGCATATACAACCTAGACTGA	Inner_Ch24-81840	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGAGACCAGGTGGCATTTC
Outer_Ch23-94941	GCTAGACTGCAAATCTACAAGC	Inner_Ch23-94941	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGCTGCTGGAATCTGAACA
Outer_Ch23-152696	AGTCTAAACAAAGCTGACTTTCA	Inner_Ch23-152696	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTAGGTGATCTTCCCTGAAA
Outer_Ch23-154331	GCAGAGGGCAGGGTTTG	Inner_Ch23-154331	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGCATTGCTCCATGACCA
Outer_Ch3-331371	TGCTACTAAAGGTCAACTCTGAAGA	Inner_Ch3-331371	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGACTCCAACCTGCTGGGA
Outer_Ch3-380135	AGGTGGTGTAAAGGGCACAG	Inner_Ch3-380135	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAGCTGGCACCAGGAGTTAA
Outer_Ch3-403847	CCATGCAACCACTCCAA	Inner_Ch3-403847	cgtgtgctctccgatctCACCTCCAATCCACCCAAA
Outer_Ch3-411447	ACACAGAAAATGTTTTCCAGGAA	Inner_Ch3-411447	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCCACAGGCTGATGACAAGA
Outer_Ch3-412336	TGTACTGAAAGTAGAAGAGAGACC	Inner_Ch3-412336	cgtgtgctctccgatctACCCAGTCCACCAAGCTCA
Outer_Ch3-424524	ACATTAAGCACAAATGTTTTAGGTG	Inner_Ch3-424524	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTAGGTGAAAGACCAAGCTGG
Outer_Ch3-430057	AGCAGAGGAGGTGCAACTATG	Inner_Ch3-430057	cgtgtgctctccgatctCTGCATGCCACTGTTTGCTT
Outer_Ch20-498734	ACCGATACAAGTATTTCTACAGTCA	Inner_Ch20-498734	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGTGGGATGTTACTTGGGT
Outer_Ch20-501240	AGTTCCTCTTGAAGCGGTATATAT	Inner_Ch20-501240	cgtgtgctctccgatctCGGCACCTGAGGATCACTGT
Outer_Ch20-513973	GGGTCAGTGCAATTTGCTGTC	Inner_Ch20-513973	cgtgtgctctccgatctAATCCAGGCACCCATGGAG
Outer_Ch20-527472	AGAAGGCAGGGTTCTGAACA	Inner_Ch20-527472	cgtgtgctctccgatctACTGCAGAACTCTTCTGCCA
Outer_Ch4A-1452702	AATGCTGTTTCATCTACTAAAGC	Inner_Ch4A-1452702	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGCAAGAAACATCATGATGCC
Outer_ChZ-2103458	TGCAAGTATTAGATGTTACCTGCC	Inner_ChZ-2103458	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCCAAAACCTTGCCTTGAG
Outer_Ch21-2119833	GGGACAGGACTCACACTTGA	Inner_Ch21-2119833	cgtgtgctctccgatctGTCAACCCGAACATTGCC
Outer_Ch21-2253374	AATTCTCAGAAATAGGGCTTGAGC	Inner_Ch21-2253374	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGGCTTGAGCTTCTTGAA
Outer_Ch21-3049512	GGCAAAGCACCTGCATCAG	Inner_Ch21-3049512	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGTCACTGTGTTGGGACA
Outer_ChZ-3694519	ACACTAAATGACTGCTCATGACTG	Inner_ChZ-3694519	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTCATAGGAGGGGTCAGGG
Outer_Ch4-4100622	TCCACAAAATGAGTGCCACT	Inner_Ch4-4100622	cgtgtgctctccgatctGAGTCCAGCATGCAAGCTCT
Outer_Ch17-4573640	ACAGGTTATGTTAAAAAGGCCAAT	Inner_Ch17-4573640	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAGATGTGGATTCTGCTTTCA
Outer_Ch5-5770310	CAGTGTAAGTCTGTCCAGTCTGA	Inner_Ch5-5770310	cgtgtgctctccgatctACACTCAGCAATGCTTCCCT
Outer_Ch15-5791745	GGTTGACAGGGACATGGATAATTTT	Inner_Ch15-5791745	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCATGAAGCAGCTCAGCTCC
Outer_Ch5-6103161	TCCAGACCATACTTGATAATTTCA	Inner_Ch5-6103161	cgtgtgctctccgatctACCAGGGCAGATACAATGCT
Outer_Ch20-6234280	CCCTGCAACACAATTAAGGAAAGA	Inner_Ch20-6234280	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCAGTCAGGCCCTCACCTCT
Outer_Ch23-6273005	ATTGATGGTGTGAGAGCTC	Inner_Ch23-6273005	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAGCTGCAAGAAAGCCAA
Outer_Ch7-6371380	TTTGTGCTTCTCTATTTAAGGACT	Inner_Ch7-6371380	cgtgtgctctccgatctTATCTGGGGTTGACAGGCT
Outer_Ch23-6483723	AATTAACCACCAGCTATCTGAGA	Inner_Ch23-6483723	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCACCAGCTATCTGAGAACTCC
Outer_Ch5-6520676	TCCATGTCAAACAGCTGAGAA	Inner_Ch5-6520676	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGGTAGCCAGCAACAGTGAA
Outer_Ch20-6700397	ATGGAAGGCAGCTATGGGG	Inner_Ch20-6700397	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCACCTTCTCCACTGCAGAT
Outer_Ch20-6700497	ATGGAAGGCAGCTATGGGG	Inner_Ch20-6700497	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCACCTTCTCCACTGCAGAT
Outer_Ch20-6700809	CAAGAGAGACTCAAAGAAACAACT	Inner_Ch20-6700809	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCAACTGCATCAAGGACCT
Outer_Ch20-6713192	AAACATGCAGATGACTTGTGC	Inner_Ch20-6713192	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCCACTGCATGACGACAAA
Outer_Ch20-6723125	AGAGCATCCTTCTCTGCTTT	Inner_Ch20-6723125	cgtgtgctctccgatctAACAGCCCTGGTATCACTG
Outer_Ch20-6728276	AGGGAAGGAAAGGTAAGAAACAA	Inner_Ch20-6728276	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGAGCATGAGAGGGGAAAGCT
Outer_Ch20-6753497	CCGAAACAACAGATTTAGGGATTAA	Inner_Ch20-6753497	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTGCAAGAAGGAGTTGTGCT
Outer_Ch20-6764550	CCCTCTGTTCTGCATGAAATCTTA	Inner_Ch20-6764550	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCTTTGTTGGCTTATCTGGGT
Outer_Ch20-6779938	TCCAGTGAATGCAGATGAGC	Inner_Ch20-6779938	cgtgtgctctccgatctGACTCCCTCAGTTTCAGGCC
Outer_Ch20-6784814	ACACCAGCTTGTATAAACTCCA	Inner_Ch20-6784814	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAGCCAACTCAGCTCTGAG
Outer_Ch23-6790657	TAATGAATCAAGAGTCACGCTG	Inner_Ch23-6790657	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCTGAGATTGGGTTGCGTTC
Outer_Ch20-6793723	TGTGCTTTGGAGTGGCTGC	Inner_Ch20-6793723	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCTCTCCCTCTTGCTGTCAG
Outer_Ch20-6861130	TGGAGGGCATATCATTATCCA	Inner_Ch20-6861130	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGCTTGCAGTGTAGGAGGAA
Outer_Ch23-6875766	TGCTTTCAACAGATCTCTAAACCC	Inner_Ch23-6875766	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCCACCACACTCACAGTAGG
Outer_Ch18-6915547	GCAGAAAGCTCCTGAAGT	Inner_Ch18-6915547	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGTACAGGAGCAACAGCAGT
Outer_Ch18-6917920	TCTGATGGATATCACCCGTTCTCA	Inner_Ch18-6917920	cgtgtgctctccgatctTAACAGGGCCTGTACAAGTGG
Outer_Ch18-6922302	TCCACTCTGAGATTTGACCT	Inner_Ch18-6922302	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGGACAAACAGCCATCTGGA
Outer_Ch13-6932052	GCAAACCTCAGTGTGTTTAAACTG	Inner_Ch13-6932052	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGGAACTTGACGCTCTGCAA
Outer_Ch20-7030563	GTATGTACAGTAACAATAGGAGCC	Inner_Ch20-7030563	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCCTGAAGATGAAATGAAAGC
Outer_Ch13-7054861	ACAACACCAATGAATTAGAGACATC	Inner_Ch13-7054861	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGAAGTCGTGTTGGTCAAGT
Outer_Ch13-7122189	GCCAGCTGCAGTCA	Inner_Ch13-7122189	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAGCTGGAGTGTCTCTGG
Outer_Ch13-7129055	TCCAAAGAAAAGAAAGATTTTCAGG	Inner_Ch13-7129055	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCCAACACAGAACACACAG
Outer_Ch26-7175007	TATTTTATGTTTATCCCTCCTCTCC	Inner_Ch26-7175007	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCTCTCTCCCTCCTCTGTTT
Outer_Ch26-7175217	TTTCTTCTTAAACTCAGATCTGC	Inner_Ch26-7175217	cgtgtgctctccgatctGATCTGCTGGGCTGGGAATT
Outer_Ch13-7180828	TCCTCTGTGCTACTAACTTGACT	Inner_Ch13-7180828	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGTTCATGGTAAAGGATACCA

Table 4. SNP (n=294) specific GUIDEseq primers (part of Genetic research protocols for studying Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita* s.l. taxa)

Type / chromosome / position	primer sequence	Type / chromosome / position	primer sequence
Outer_Ch20-7233096	TGGTGTCTGAATGTGACAAAATAA	Inner_Ch20-7233096	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAGTGTGACTTGTGAGCT
Outer_Ch23-7254729	GTTTCCCACGGGGTAGTTCC	Inner_Ch23-7254729	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCTTCCGAGCTAACACGA
Outer_Ch23-7260312	AGTGGTCTTTGAAATACCACTCTAA	Inner_Ch23-7260312	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGTTAGGCCAGGAGAACAC
Outer_Ch23-7274199	GACCTGGAAGGCATTTGAAGAAA	Inner_Ch23-7274199	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGGGATTTCTATTTGGCCCA
Outer_Ch23-7276555	TGGGTGTTTTGGCTTGGTTTT	Inner_Ch23-7276555	cgtgtgctctccgatctAAGCTGCTGCAGCTGACTA
Outer_ChZ-7290726	ACACAGGCATATCATTACCAACA	Inner_ChZ-7290726	cgtgtgctctccgatctCATGTTCCAGCCGCCACATC
Outer_Ch23-7327293	TCCTCTTCTCTCCAAGGTGAA	Inner_Ch23-7327293	cgtgtgctctccgatctCATGCAGGAGGAAGGGTGT
Outer_Ch13-7426976	ATTGTCTGGACATACAATCTGC	Inner_Ch13-7426976	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGCAAAGACAAATTCACCTGCA
Outer_Ch26-7435262	GCAATATATCACATGTTCTTAAGG	Inner_Ch26-7435262	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCTGTCACTGGAGGGCTTAG
Outer_ChZ-7539581	TCCTTCCCTTGCTGAAACTTT	Inner_ChZ-7539581	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGGGTAGAGCCAAAACCCAG
Outer_ChZ-7540597	TCTCATTAGTTTGTGTAGTCAGT	Inner_ChZ-7540597	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTGTCTGGGGATGAAGCTG
Outer_Ch13-7739531	TGTGTTCCATTTAAGTAACAGCCT	Inner_Ch13-7739531	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAGTCTGAATGCATGCAGGC
Outer_Ch13-7750015	CTTCCCTTGGCTTGTCCCAT	Inner_Ch13-7750015	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTAGTGGGACATGTGCAGG
Outer_Ch13-7929278	TCCAAGGACCAGAGACCTGT	Inner_Ch13-7929278	cgtgtgctctccgatctGTGGAGAGCAGAGCTTCTGG
Outer_Ch13-7929279	TCCAAGGACCAGAGACCTGT	Inner_Ch13-7929279	cgtgtgctctccgatctGTGGAGAGCAGAGCTTCTGG
Outer_Ch13-7933015	CCTCAAGTGTGGTTTCATGGA	Inner_Ch13-7933015	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGCTCACTTCTGTGACAGTC
Outer_Ch13-7937961	CTAAATGAAGTATGGAAGTTTGGCA	Inner_Ch13-7937961	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCATTGCCCTCAGAGTCCA
Outer_Ch13-7946911	TCTGCAAGTAAGTTGGGTTGG	Inner_Ch13-7946911	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGAAGGTTACATGGTCCAGC
Outer_Ch13-7952006	TGCAAGAAAGCAGTATTGATTATCA	Inner_Ch13-7952006	cgtgtgctctccgatctACTGCCAACCTCAGTTTTGCA
Outer_Ch12-8403730	CCATCTTTGGGATAGTTTTCAAGT	Inner_Ch12-8403730	cgtgtgctctccgatctGTAGCCACTCAACTGCCCTT
Outer_Ch12-8655487	ACAGATGGACAAAAGTTATTCTGAG	Inner_Ch12-8655487	cgtgtgctctccgatctAAGCCTCAGAGGAAGTCTC
Outer_Ch12-8668265	CCTTTGGGCTCATACTCAGCT	Inner_Ch12-8668265	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCTAAGCGCAATCACACCAG
Outer_Ch12-8668390	TGAAAGTTGAGGTACATCATGACT	Inner_Ch12-8668390	cgtgtgctctccgatctACTGCCAAGACTCTGCCATC
Outer_Ch12-8753039	ACACTTGTCTCCAGAATGC	Inner_Ch12-8753039	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGCTGAACAGTGTGAGTGGGTG
Outer_Ch12-8798215	AGTGAGTTAAAACCTGAGTAGAACCA	Inner_Ch12-8798215	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAGTCTGAGGACAGCAACA
Outer_Ch12-8839329	AAAAGAGCATACAGGAAATCTTGTT	Inner_Ch12-8839329	cgtgtgctctccgatctATCCCGGGTCAAAGGACATT
Outer_Ch12-8844898	TGAACACTCAATCTATTGTGACAGAG	Inner_Ch12-8844898	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAAAAGCCAGTCATCAGCC
Outer_Ch12-8937578	AGGGTATTTCTGTTTTGTTTTGCT	Inner_Ch12-8937578	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCTGTGAGCATAATCCATCTCTGA
Outer_Ch12-8941183	ACAGAACTTTGCATTACAGCTGT	Inner_Ch12-8941183	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGGGTTTTCTGCTCTGCTTCA
Outer_Ch12-9038025	TCTGTCTCCCTGCAGACCAG	Inner_Ch12-9038025	cgtgtgctctccgatctGAGGGAGTGTTCAGGGAAGC
Outer_Ch12-9043764	GCAAATGGAAATCTAATGCTTCAAAA	Inner_Ch12-9043764	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCTCTGAGGCTCAGGATGTC
Outer_Ch12-9048487	CACACACAAGCATGAACAAAAGAA	Inner_Ch12-9048487	cgtgtgctctccgatctACAGCGCAGTGAAGTTACA
Outer_Ch12-9050796	AAAAATAAGTGAGTGCTGTTGGT	Inner_Ch12-9050796	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGTGTCTTTGGTAAACGGTCC
Outer_Ch12-9055839	CTGGTCAAAGTACAACACTGCA	Inner_Ch12-9055839	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCACCTGGAGCAGATGAGTT
Outer_Ch12-9069734	GGCGAGTAAGACAGAATCCAATAGT	Inner_Ch12-9069734	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGCCCTCACAGTTTGCATCT
Outer_Ch12-9072579	AAGGGAAAGAAATCAATACAACCAC	Inner_Ch12-9072579	cgtgtgctctccgatctCACCTGTTACTGCCCTCTCTG
Outer_Ch12-9081230	TCCACAAAAGCATGACTAAGACT	Inner_Ch12-9081230	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGTGAAGTGGTCTCAGTGG
Outer_Ch12-9089237	GGTGAGTCATACAACCTGTGAAAGC	Inner_Ch12-9089237	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGTGAGGAGCGTTGAAAAATGG
Outer_Ch12-9099888	TGTAAGGTACACTACATTTGCTCA	Inner_Ch12-9099888	cgtgtgctctccgatctAAACAGCTGTCAGGAGTGCA
Outer_Ch12-9105311	TGGCTGCAGAAGAAAATCTTTTT	Inner_Ch12-9105311	cgtgtgctctccgatctACAGGGACACACGTGTTTCT
Outer_Ch12-9111651	TGCTGAAGGAGAGTTAAGGCA	Inner_Ch12-9111651	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGGTAGCAAGGGGAGCAAT
Outer_Ch12-9114758	GTTTTGCTTCACTTGAGAAACCC	Inner_Ch12-9114758	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCCAGTACCTACAGTCCCTGA
Outer_Ch12-9117753	GCTGGGGCTGCACTG	Inner_Ch12-9117753	cgtgtgctctccgatctCTGGGAGCAGGAGGACAAG
Outer_Ch12-9130245	GCTGTGATACTTCTAAGGTGACT	Inner_Ch12-9130245	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGAGGACAGCTGATATCAAG
Outer_Ch12-9139942	ACCAATGGTGAAAATCAGGGGTA	Inner_Ch12-9139942	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGAGCAGAAGTCATGGTGCT
Outer_Ch12-9143702	ACGCACTGTATCACAAGTTCC	Inner_Ch12-9143702	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCCAGTAGGCTTGTGTGCTC
Outer_Ch12-9147061	TGATTGAATCAGCTTTTCCACAGT	Inner_Ch12-9147061	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCCAGCTGGCAAGAACACA
Outer_Ch12-9159017	TCTTCCAGTTAGATTTGAACTCT	Inner_Ch12-9159017	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGGCAATGGGACTACACATTCT
Outer_Ch12-9163138	ACAATCTCACGGAAATGTCTGA	Inner_Ch12-9163138	cgtgtgctctccgatctACTGGGTTTGTCTGGGACA
Outer_Ch12-9355062	GCTCTGCAGCTATGATGTTAAATAT	Inner_Ch12-9355062	cgtgtgctctccgatctAACCCGTGTGGAAAGTGTTA
Outer_Ch12-9355984	GCAATTACCAGCCATTTAGTAAAGA	Inner_Ch12-9355984	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCAGGTGGCTTCTTTTATTGGT
Outer_Ch12-9367373	TGTCACCAGCAACAGTTACAG	Inner_Ch12-9367373	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAGCGGATGAAGGAAAACGC
Outer_Ch12-9608946	GCTGCAAGTCAACACACTTCT	Inner_Ch12-9608946	cgtgtgctctccgatctGTGGCCTTGATGAGCCTTCT
Outer_Ch14-9938448	TCCTCATGGCTGAAACCTGC	Inner_Ch14-9938448	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCCTGATCTTTGGACTGGCT
Outer_Ch14-9939304	CCGCTCTATTCAAGGTTATTAGAAC	Inner_Ch14-9939304	cgtgtgctctccgatctTACCCTGCTGCAGGTTAGC
Outer_Ch14-9943053	ACTCTGCAAGGCTTTAATTAGTAGT	Inner_Ch14-9943053	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTGTCAGGAAAGTCTGCCT
Outer_Ch12-10006403	GATCAATTATTGGAGTACCCTTTGT	Inner_Ch12-10006403	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGATGACACACAGCTCAGATGA
Outer_Ch14-10209751	TTCATTAGTTAATTGTGGAGTAGG	Inner_Ch14-10209751	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGGGGGAGTTTGAAGCAGT
Outer_Ch14-10209833	TTCATTAGTTAATTGTGGAGTAGG	Inner_Ch14-10209833	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGGGGGAGTTTGAAGCAGT
Outer_Ch14-10211731	TCAAAGATTTCTTAAGGGAAAACC	Inner_Ch14-10211731	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTGGGGGAGAAAAGTACCT
Outer_Ch14-10212717	ACTTCAGAAAAGTCTTTGACATCC	Inner_Ch14-10212717	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCCTTCTCTGTAGGCGGAA
Outer_Ch14-10214169	AGCATTTCATATGTCACTGTACTCT	Inner_Ch14-10214169	cgtgtgctctccgatctCTTCTGATGCAGCTTGA
Outer_Ch14-10214307	TGCTTAGGCAATAACTACTCCAG	Inner_Ch14-10214307	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAGCCATGGCAGTCAATCAT
Outer_Ch14-10214527	TGGGGTGAGATGAACTTGAAGG	Inner_Ch14-10214527	cgtgtgctctccgatctGTCCCTTCAACCCAAACCA
Outer_Ch14-10214791	CTTCATCTGATTGAAGCACAAAATG	Inner_Ch14-10214791	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGTTTATCCAAAACCCAGCT

Table 4. SNP (n=294) specific GUIDEseq primers (part of Genetic research protocols for studying Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita* s.l. taxa)

Type / chromosome / position	primer sequence	Type / chromosome / position	primer sequence
Outer_Ch14-10217148	TCATGTCCTGCACAGCTTGA	Inner_Ch14-10217148	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGAGACTGACTGCTTGCTGT
Outer_Ch14-10231050	AGAAATGGATTCTGTAACACAGGTA	Inner_Ch14-10231050	cgtgtgctctccgatctACCCACAGTGAACACTTTCA
Outer_Ch14-10231196	TGACTGATAGAGAAATACCCAGACT	Inner_Ch14-10231196	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCAGCAGTTGAACACTTGCA
Outer_Ch12-10247912	TCACTTGTACAGCTGTAATAACTCT	Inner_Ch12-10247912	cgtgtgctctccgatctATGCTGCCCTCACTCCAGTC
Outer_Ch14-10373398	AGTTGAGAACTCTGGAGTCAAACCT	Inner_Ch14-10373398	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGATCTGTACACTGGAGGG
Outer_Ch14-10386816	CTGACCAGCTCAATACTGCT	Inner_Ch14-10386816	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCTGCAGCTTCCATGTAGC
Outer_Ch14-10389236	AGTTTGGAGAAAGAAGGGATCCT	Inner_Ch14-10389236	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGAGGGAGGAAGCACATGGA
Outer_Ch14-10398363	CAGAAAACCAAACCTGCTACTCCA	Inner_Ch14-10398363	cgtgtgctctccgatctCGTGCAGTAAACTGTGCTG
Outer_Ch14-10451327	TTTACCAGTTGGGGCTTGCC	Inner_Ch14-10451327	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCAGTCTGCAAAACAGTCT
Outer_Ch14-10769390	GGAACTTTTTCTGGTCATACTCTC	Inner_Ch14-10769390	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGAAGTACAGCTACATGGTGA
Outer_Ch7-11171193	AGTTTTATTGCCAAAGTTGACGAAG	Inner_Ch7-11171193	cgtgtgctctccgatctGACAGTACCCAAACCCACTA
Outer_ChZ-11253349	TGGACCACTGTTTTAGCAA	Inner_ChZ-11253349	cgtgtgctctccgatctCTGTGACAGGCGCATCTAC
Outer_Ch12-11699207	CCCAGTATTGAATTGGGGTTGC	Inner_Ch12-11699207	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGCTAGAGCGGCACAAAT
Outer_Ch12-11736959	CAGTCAATACCTGGACAACGTTT	Inner_Ch12-11736959	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGGATTACAGGAATAGGGCCG
Outer_Ch10-12024943	AATCATACTCAGAGCCTTTTGC	Inner_Ch10-12024943	cgtgtgctctccgatctCTGGGGTGGTGAAGTGAAAA
Outer_Ch3-12244364	GGTGACAGTACAGTAAATAAAAAGT	Inner_Ch3-12244364	cgtgtgctctccgatctTATCAGCAGGGTAGGCTCT
Outer_Ch17-12258707	GGTCCATCCAATCTAAACTGGT	Inner_Ch17-12258707	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGATTAGGCAGCTGCTGAC
Outer_Ch3-12268579	TGCTTTCACCTTTAGCAAGAAGAG	Inner_Ch3-12268579	cgtgtgctctccgatctACTGAACCTCTGCAAGTGT
Outer_Ch3-12336737	AGGGACATATCACAGCAGCTG	Inner_Ch3-12336737	cgtgtgctctccgatctCTGTGGACTCCATGAGG
Outer_Ch10-12443279	CAGAGTATCTGTGTGACAGGGT	Inner_Ch10-12443279	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTTGCTGCCATCCCATGTTT
Outer_Ch10-12448976	AGGATACCAGACCTGTTAGGTCA	Inner_Ch10-12448976	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCCCTCAGGTCCAATGATG
Outer_Ch12-12500473	TGAACAATGTGCTTTATTTGGGGA	Inner_Ch12-12500473	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGAAGAGTGAGCTGTGAGGG
Outer_Ch10-12523750	CAGGCTGGCAGTGAACAAG	Inner_Ch10-12523750	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCATGTTGCTGACCAAGCG
Outer_Ch10-12528030	TTAAGCTTAACTCTGGAGATCCTC	Inner_Ch10-12528030	cgtgtgctctccgatctCTCAGACGTTTCAGCCAGCT
Outer_Ch10-12572970	CCTCTCCTGTCTCTTCTGAGG	Inner_Ch10-12572970	cgtgtgctctccgatctGAGCAAGCAGCAGAACACC
Outer_Ch10-12576035	AACAGATGCCAGTGACATGA	Inner_Ch10-12576035	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGACAGAGGGCTTTGGCAAA
Outer_Ch10-12620374	ATGAGTGTTTCATGCACCCT	Inner_Ch10-12620374	cgtgtgctctccgatctACATTTGCTTTGGCTGCTGG
Outer_Ch10-12620963	ACAGCACACAGATATCCAGGATAAA	Inner_Ch10-12620963	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCAAAAACCTGAGGAGGCA
Outer_Ch10-12634886	TGGAATGTTTTGATCATAAAGGGT	Inner_Ch10-12634886	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGCTGCAGGTCTGTAGATGT
Outer_Ch10-12637197	TGCTTGAATCATCTCAGATTGTG	Inner_Ch10-12637197	cgtgtgctctccgatctACAGTTGCCTTTCAGAGCCC
Outer_Ch10-12651548	AGGGAGAGAAAGGCAAACTTA	Inner_Ch10-12651548	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCAGGGCTCTTCTAAAGCA
Outer_Ch10-12661922	GGTGAACACCAACTAGCTATG	Inner_Ch10-12661922	cgtgtgctctccgatctATGCCATTAGCCTGTGTGG
Outer_Ch3-12756598	TGTCTCAGTGTTCTTTACTTCAGT	Inner_Ch3-12756598	cgtgtgctctccgatctCACAGGTGGCATCTGCTGTA
Outer_ChZ-12756992	ACAAGAGACATTTAACACAGACAG	Inner_ChZ-12756992	cgtgtgctctccgatctACAGACAGTGTCTTAGGGA
Outer_Ch10-12770297	AATTGCTCAGTTGTAAGAATATGT	Inner_Ch10-12770297	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGTGAGCGTGGTACTGACAA
Outer_Ch3-12852046	TGGGGAAAGAGTCACATAGAGAA	Inner_Ch3-12852046	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAGCATCCCTACTGCAGAA
Outer_Ch10-12869688	TCCAACTATTTTCAAAGCAGATT	Inner_Ch10-12869688	cgtgtgctctccgatctGATCAGCAGCTTCTGAGCA
Outer_Ch10-12890343	GCATTGTCTTTAGCAAAAAGAGAT	Inner_Ch10-12890343	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGGGGTTTTTCAGCAGCAGA
Outer_Ch10-12901257	CCTTTTGTTCTATCTTACATGTT	Inner_Ch10-12901257	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAGAACTGTGGTAGAACAAACCA
Outer_Ch10-12906883	GTGCTGGGCTCACTCTGG	Inner_Ch10-12906883	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCTGCCAGGTAGTAATCGCT
Outer_Ch3-12925126	ACCTCACCAATTTTATGTGAATT	Inner_Ch3-12925126	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAGGGCTTTTGGTGTACC
Outer_Ch10-12927821	AAACTTTCTTTCTGCTGTGTTTT	Inner_Ch10-12927821	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGGGTGGAGGTTGGTATTGG
Outer_Ch10-12935910	CCAACTTGGCTGCAACTG	Inner_Ch10-12935910	cgtgtgctctccgatctCTGGACTCCTCAGCAACA
Outer_Ch3-12982526	TCCAGTAATCCACCAGAAGAAAT	Inner_Ch3-12982526	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGTTCGCCAAATCTCCACT
Outer_Ch10-12988547	TGATCACACTTGACGTCTGT	Inner_Ch10-12988547	cgtgtgctctccgatctTACATGGTACCTGGCTGTG
Outer_Ch3-12993101	TCAGGCCTGTAGTTCTTATATTGG	Inner_Ch3-12993101	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGGGGACTGCATTTGGATTT
Outer_Ch5-13131834	CCTCTCCTTTCTCTTTTCTGTCT	Inner_Ch5-13131834	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCTTTCTTTCTGGCAGCA
Outer_Ch5-13139637	AGCATGGCTGAAGACTAATCTTAAT	Inner_Ch5-13139637	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTGTTCTTCCACTGGAGGC
Outer_Ch5-13162210	GTCTGTCTGAGAGATGAGTAAA	Inner_Ch5-13162210	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTCAGCACAACTTTGCGG
Outer_Ch5-13168069	TTACAGTAGAAATTAAGGCAAGACC	Inner_Ch5-13168069	cgtgtgctctccgatctCTGGAGTTTCCAGCTGCCAGA
Outer_Ch10-13201831	GAGTGCTAAATCCACTACAAGTTAA	Inner_Ch10-13201831	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGCAAGATGGAAGCTGAGGC
Outer_Ch5-13208401	TGAGAAGGAAAAGATGAAGCACT	Inner_Ch5-13208401	cgtgtgctctccgatctACTTGCCTCAGTCCCAAGG
Outer_Ch5-13209329	TCAAACCTAACTCCAGATAGCGC	Inner_Ch5-13209329	cgtgtgctctccgatctCGCAGACAAATCACCATGCC
Outer_Ch3-13210856	TGCTTTCTAGGCAGGTAATTACAT	Inner_Ch3-13210856	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGCCACACTTACTACTGGCT
Outer_Ch5-13217607	ACTATTGCAGAACCATCAGTGT	Inner_Ch5-13217607	cgtgtgctctccgatctAAGCCTTGAAGCCTTGGTGA
Outer_Ch5-13219155	GGTTTGGCTGATGGACCTCA	Inner_Ch5-13219155	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGCTTACTGCTCCTCAACTG
Outer_Ch5-13221020	ACACACCTCAAACCTCTGGT	Inner_Ch5-13221020	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGTCTCTCCTTGGACCCAGA
Outer_Ch5-13221474	CACAGGTTGGTATAATTCCTACTCA	Inner_Ch5-13221474	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGCAACTGAAGCCTTCCACA
Outer_Ch5-13224612	TCCTGAAACAACAGTGAGCA	Inner_Ch5-13224612	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCACTGCTGTGCTTAAATC
Outer_Ch5-13227488	TGTACAGACATAGTCTCTGAAGC	Inner_Ch5-13227488	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGCAAACCTCAAGGGCTGTCA
Outer_Ch5-13231672	TAACCTTACCCTTTTCAATGTGG	Inner_Ch5-13231672	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGTGGGCACATGTTGGGA
Outer_Ch3-13236575	TCAGAGAGGGTTTTCTGTCTAATTTT	Inner_Ch3-13236575	cgtgtgctctccgatctACGAGGACAGCTTTCACACT
Outer_Ch10-13271954	TTCTTAAACGGGCTGAAGTGC	Inner_Ch10-13271954	cgtgtgctctccgatctGTTGGCTTGCAAGAGGTTGG
Outer_Ch5-13296658	CCACAATGGTCAGGAGCTTG	Inner_Ch5-13296658	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTGGTGAATGAGCCATCC
Outer_Ch10-13546279	TCCAAACAATTTACCCTACTACAGCTG	Inner_Ch10-13546279	cgtgtgctctccgatctACCAAATCTGTAGCTTCTGAAGA

Table 4. SNP (n=294) specific GUIDEseq primers (part of Genetic research protocols for studying Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita* s.l. taxa)

Type / chromosome / position	primer sequence	Type / chromosome / position	primer sequence
Outer_Chr5-13645109	TTTTTGGCAGTTGCAGTCTG	Inner_Chr5-13645109	cgtgtgctctccgatctCGAATCCTGTGGTGACCTA
Outer_Chr5-13957520	CACTCTTACACAACCACTTGAATCA	Inner_Chr5-13957520	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGTTTTGGCTTCCAGGGCT
Outer_Chr5-14168974	TCACACATACAGCAGGCATAGT	Inner_Chr5-14168974	cgtgtgctctccgatctACCAGGTGTGAGAAGCAGTG
Outer_Chr5-14187643	CTCTTCCCAGTGAGTATCAGCC	Inner_Chr5-14187643	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCCAACGTGCAGCACTAAAT
Outer_Chr10-14209228	ACACCCACAAACATTCTATGAGA	Inner_Chr10-14209228	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGATGCACAGCACCAGTGAA
Outer_Chr5-14213193	TCCAAACTCCTCTATCATGGA	Inner_Chr5-14213193	cgtgtgctctccgatctCATCTGGACAGGACCAAGCA
Outer_Chr5-14225337	GGTGATAGGCAGTACTATGTTGC	Inner_Chr5-14225337	cgtgtgctctccgatctAAGCTGCTCAGTCTTGCCAA
Outer_Chr5-14241814	ACCACCTCTATGAAGCTATTTTAGT	Inner_Chr5-14241814	cgtgtgctctccgatctAAGGGGCGAAAAGGGTTTGA
Outer_Chr10-14274053	AGTAAGGCTCAAAGAGTATAAGGG	Inner_Chr10-14274053	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGGTGCAAGTCTCTCCCAA
Outer_Chr5-14303390	CCCAACAATTAAGACTACCAGAACA	Inner_Chr5-14303390	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCATCAGCTGGCAAGTCCCTG
Outer_Chr5-14325242	TGATAATACCTGGTTGCATAACTA	Inner_Chr5-14325242	cgtgtgctctccgatctCTGTGTCCAGATGCAGTGT
Outer_Chr5-14330680	GCAGTAGCTGTAGCCAGTTTC	Inner_Chr5-14330680	cgtgtgctctccgatctACTGAATGGGCAGTCTGT
Outer_Chr5-14333420	GTGTTTCAGCACAGCAGAAGA	Inner_Chr5-14333420	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCCCAAACTGCATGATGG
Outer_Chr10-14440784	ACTTCAAACCGTTGCCTCTGT	Inner_Chr10-14440784	cgtgtgctctccgatctGAGTGGCTGAGATCTTGCA
Outer_Chr10-14640640	CCTTCTCCTCTGTACCAACTGA	Inner_Chr10-14640640	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCTCTGAGCAGGAACACT
Outer_Chr10-14652190	TGTCAGTACCACATACAAACACA	Inner_Chr10-14652190	cgtgtgctctccgatctAACAGTAAGAACCTGGCCC
Outer_Chr10-14666531	GCAGTGAGATCAAACCCACC	Inner_Chr10-14666531	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGCTCTGGACACTGCTTGAG
Outer_Chr10-14732420	ACTGCAGTTCTTTTTGATTTTGT	Inner_Chr10-14732420	cgtgtgctctccgatctCTGTGCTACTTGTATCTCCA
Outer_Chr10-14745735	AGTGCTGGCATTACAATCTAAAGA	Inner_Chr10-14745735	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGCCTTGCTGCAGTAGATGG
Outer_Chr10-14751460	GGTTGTTTTCTAACTTACAGGGATT	Inner_Chr10-14751460	cgtgtgctctccgatctCTCTCCTGCAGTTCCTACCA
Outer_Chr10-15247557	CTTGCCCTTTTTAACTTTGATATGG	Inner_Chr10-15247557	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGGGGATCTGTAGCATTGGG
Outer_Chr10-15271209	TGTGATGGATAGCAGCCAGG	Inner_Chr10-15271209	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGGCAGACACATTAGCCAC
Outer_Chr10-15287150	AGACCATACATATAAGCAGCAGT	Inner_Chr10-15287150	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGGCTGCATACCTTCAGCAT
Outer_Chr7-18176967	CCTCTGATGTGTTTTAAGTACCCAA	Inner_Chr7-18176967	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGCTCTCTTCTGTGCTGCT
Outer_Chr4A-18351803	TGCCTTATCAGTGTTTTCCCCA	Inner_Chr4A-18351803	cgtgtgctctccgatctGTGATGTCACCTGCTGGGAA
Outer_Chr7-19860197	AGGGTCTTGAATTAAGTACTGGA	Inner_Chr7-19860197	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCCTAATTAAGCACCCTTTTCT
Outer_Chr7-19862967	TGTAACAGAAATTTGTAACCTAGGC	Inner_Chr7-19862967	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGCAGTCTTTCAGCTCTTCG
Outer_Chr7-19863673	TGCATGATGTAGTTATTAGCTCATG	Inner_Chr7-19863673	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGCTATCTTCCAAACCC
Outer_Chr7-19877305	ACATGGCCTATATTCTATCTGCTT	Inner_Chr7-19877305	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGGAAACCATCAGATTGGCACT
Outer_Chr7-19877309	ACATGGCCTATATTCTATCTGCTT	Inner_Chr7-19877309	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGGAAACCATCAGATTGGCACT
Outer_Chr7-19882781	CACTCTAGGATCAGTCAAAATGTTT	Inner_Chr7-19882781	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGCTGGAATATAGGGAAGCA
Outer_Chr7-19883365	TTGTGGAATCTTGCAATTATTTCCA	Inner_Chr7-19883365	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTTGTGTCCAAGGGCATGGT
Outer_Chr7-19901968	CCTGTGTTCTAGAAATGTGCAAAAT	Inner_Chr7-19901968	cgtgtgctctccgatctACGATTCATGGCTACCCAGC
Outer_Chr8-26502755	AACTAGTGCTTCTGAAACCGT	Inner_Chr8-26502755	cgtgtgctctccgatctTATTGTCCCAAACCTGCC
Outer_ChrZ-28539406	TAAGAGCAGGGTGAGGCTTG	Inner_ChrZ-28539406	cgtgtgctctccgatctACTGCACAGCTTTCTCACA
Outer_ChrZ-28917575	AGGAATGTGAACAGATTGAAAAC	Inner_ChrZ-28917575	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAGATGCTGGTGTATGGCCC
Outer_ChrZ-29198019	AAACCTGCAGTCTGCTTGG	Inner_ChrZ-29198019	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAGTGTGTCACAGTTC
Outer_ChrZ-29928433	TGTTAAGCCAAAACACTCTGGA	Inner_ChrZ-29928433	cgtgtgctctccgatctGAGGAGGTGCAGCAGACAAA
Outer_ChrZ-36164631	ACACATATTGGCTGACATTTATCAC	Inner_ChrZ-36164631	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCCTCCAGACTTCTCCAA
Outer_ChrZ-38520782	TCACCCAGGTGCTTATCTCTC	Inner_ChrZ-38520782	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCTTGCTGCTGACATCTG
Outer_Chr1A-48551041	TTCTCTCTCTCTGGCTCT	Inner_Chr1A-48551041	cgtgtgctctccgatctGAGGGAGCTTTGGAGTGTGA
Outer_Chr1A-48621080	TGCTCATACTTCCCCACAC	Inner_Chr1A-48621080	cgtgtgctctccgatctACTAATCCAGGTTGCAGC
Outer_Chr1A-49184589	TGCTACAGGGAAATCAAAGTATAT	Inner_Chr1A-49184589	cgtgtgctctccgatctACAAGGTATGGTGTGTGAC
Outer_Chr1A-49186670	GGAAAGCTTCTGAAAGTTCTCCAG	Inner_Chr1A-49186670	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCTTGTGGAGCAGCAGACG
Outer_Chr1A-49193967	TCCGTAGTGACACTAGTTGATGC	Inner_Chr1A-49193967	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCACATGGAGGCTCATCAA
Outer_Chr1A-49231172	GCATTCAAGATGTGAGCTATGGA	Inner_Chr1A-49231172	cgtgtgctctccgatctACAGAGCAGGGCTTGAAGTT
Outer_Chr1A-49231222	TTTTGTGGCAGCTGGGACTC	Inner_Chr1A-49231222	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTCCAAGTGGCTGAGCAGAG
Outer_Chr1A-49246302	GCCCTTAAATCTACTCTTTGTCT	Inner_Chr1A-49246302	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGTGCTTCTCTGCCATTA
Outer_Chr1A-49283406	AGCTTTTTAGTATCAAATGCATGGT	Inner_Chr1A-49283406	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGCAAGCATCAGGGAACACA
Outer_Chr1A-49308476	TTCTCCACTCTTTATGTTGCTT	Inner_Chr1A-49308476	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGGGAGCTTCTTCTTGCCTT
Outer_Chr1A-49390362	AGGATAGAGAGGGTGAGACTTCA	Inner_Chr1A-49390362	cgtgtgctctccgatctAACCTTCTACTGGGCGAGAG
Outer_Chr1A-49438781	TGCTCTCATGTTAAATGAGGGG	Inner_Chr1A-49438781	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGGAAAGGAAAGGACAGCT
Outer_Chr1A-49476521	AGTTCCTGCACATTTCCAG	Inner_Chr1A-49476521	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTGTGGCTAGCAGAACCTCG
Outer_Chr1A-49499537	ACCAAACCCAAACAAACCATCA	Inner_Chr1A-49499537	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCACTATTTGGCTTGCAGC
Outer_Chr1A-49717140	AGGAACCTGAGTGTGAGTATGC	Inner_Chr1A-49717140	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGCTGGTCCAGTCTTTTCA
Outer_Chr1A-49877312	TGGACATGACACTCACCTTG	Inner_Chr1A-49877312	cgtgtgctctccgatctACCTCAGCTCCCAACTGC
Outer_Chr1A-50106460	TGCTCTCATATACTCTCTGCGTTT	Inner_Chr1A-50106460	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTCCAAGGCTGCTTCTCT
Outer_Chr1A-50125481	CAGCTTCTGATGGATGCCATT	Inner_Chr1A-50125481	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGCCAAGGTGTTCCAGAGCAA
Outer_Chr1A-50243185	TCGGTGGTCTGGAACCTGTG	Inner_Chr1A-50243185	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGCTGACAAGGGCACTACTG
Outer_Chr1A-50270004	TGGCTTTTATCTTTGGGTTTCAAAT	Inner_Chr1A-50270004	cgtgtgctctccgatctTACAGACTCACGAAAACCTACT
Outer_Chr1A-50369793	GCACAGACTTGAACAAAATGCTAA	Inner_Chr1A-50369793	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCAAGCTCTACCAACGACA
Outer_Chr1A-50456053	CTCAAAGTGCCTTTCACAGACCA	Inner_Chr1A-50456053	cgtgtgctctccgatctACCTCCCAACTCTGATACC
Outer_Chr1A-50565887	CCTTAATGTTTGCAGTCTTCTAAGA	Inner_Chr1A-50565887	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGGAGTAAAGGTGGTGTGG
Outer_Chr1A-50747939	ATGACTCTGCCTGATGTGGA	Inner_Chr1A-50747939	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGAAGTCCCTGGCAGAAACA
Outer_Chr1A-50761404	TGTGTTTTAGTCAAGAAAACCC	Inner_Chr1A-50761404	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCCACGACCTAAAAGCCAT

Table 4. SNP (n=294) specific GUIDEseq primers (part of Genetic research protocols for studying Chiffchaff *Phylloscopus collybita* s.l. taxa)

Type / chromosome / position	primer sequence	Type / chromosome / position	primer sequence
Outer_Ch1A-50786743	TCACTGAATAGACAGAGACGCT	Inner_Ch1A-50786743	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCTGATGCCAACACTTCTG
Outer_Ch1A-50788286	TTTTGAAGGCTACAGTTCTATCCT	Inner_Ch1A-50788286	cgtgtgctctccgatctTAAGAGTCCCCCTGGTCAG
Outer_Ch1A-50827664	ACACCAACTAAAATCTACACCTGT	Inner_Ch1A-50827664	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCTTCAGGCTGTACCACAC
Outer_Ch1A-50839715	TGCAATAGAAACAAGAGCAGTTTGT	Inner_Ch1A-50839715	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGGGCAAAGTGCTTAGCAGA
Outer_Ch1A-50850747	ACCTGGAATGAAAAGAAGTAAAGT	Inner_Ch1A-50850747	cgtgtgctctccgatctCGGACTCATGCTTCACTCTCA
Outer_Ch1A-51542299	GGGGAATGATTGAACCACTTACT	Inner_Ch1A-51542299	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCTTCCCTTTTGTGCATCC
Outer_Ch1A-51607939	TCAGAGAAGTTACAGTCAGTCAGA	Inner_Ch1A-51607939	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGGTGCTTCTTGGGAGCAAA
Outer_Ch1A-51856439	AAGCTGGACTATTAGACATAAGCT	Inner_Ch1A-51856439	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGACGGGAAAGAAGACAGCA
Outer_Ch1A-51874751	ACCAGAATCCCTTCCCAGG	Inner_Ch1A-51874751	cgtgtgctctccgatctCTGCCAGATTGCACACCAG
Outer_Ch2-57179677	TGACACTGGATTCACAATTGTTTT	Inner_Ch2-57179677	cgtgtgctctccgatctCTGCCTTGATGCCACAAACA
Outer_Ch2-57978389	AAAGATTTGTATTGGTATGGACCCA	Inner_Ch2-57978389	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGGACCCACAGAATCTGAACA
Outer_Ch2-58286546	TGAGCTGTTTCAAGATGGTAAATCC	Inner_Ch2-58286546	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGAGCTTGGACACAGGAC
Outer_Ch2-77089378	AGTTGTGATCCACCTCTCTTGT	Inner_Ch2-77089378	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGGCAAAGGAGCACAGAGAG
Outer_Ch2-78675063	TGTTTTAGTGAGCATTTCAGCC	Inner_Ch2-78675063	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGCATTTCAGCCTGAAGCCA
Outer_Ch2-78694055	TCGACACCATTGATTTTTCATAGTT	Inner_Ch2-78694055	cgtgtgctctccgatctTAAGTCCCTGGCACCTTAGC
Outer_Ch1-102874273	CTTCCTTCTCTCTGCCACC	Inner_Ch1-102874273	cgtgtgctctccgatctCATGACACAGTCACTGCCCT
Outer_Ch1-103016514	TCCATTTACAGTTGTAGAATTAGTC	Inner_Ch1-103016514	cgtgtgctctccgatctGGTTGTGCTTTGAGCCTCCT
Outer_Ch1-103060920	GGACTCAGTGGGAAACATAAGCA	Inner_Ch1-103060920	cgtgtgctctccgatctCAAGTCCAGTGCAGCAGAG
Outer_Ch1-104140607	TGTCCTTATTTGGAACCTTCTGAAGT	Inner_Ch1-104140607	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCCAGGAAAGACAGGGTTT
Outer_Ch1-104175412	TAAAAGAAGTTAATTCACCTCAGGG	Inner_Ch1-104175412	cgtgtgctctccgatctAATTCACCTCAGGGGACAGC
Outer_Ch1-104232351	TTTTTCTTCTCTGAGCATTCTTCT	Inner_Ch1-104232351	cgtgtgctctccgatctTTCTTCTCAGAGGCTCCCCA
Outer_Ch1-104244214	TCTTTGCTGAACCTGTTCTGG	Inner_Ch1-104244214	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGGGAATTCATGTGCCAGT
Outer_Ch1-104245621	AGCCTCAAACCAATTGCAATCA	Inner_Ch1-104245621	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCTTGCTGTGGGTGCTTCT
Outer_Ch1-104255844	GGTGGGAAGAATAGGGTTGCAGA	Inner_Ch1-104255844	cgtgtgctctccgatctAGGAAGTTTGGTCCAGGCAG
Outer_Ch1-104256518	ACAACCACTCACAATCAGTGT	Inner_Ch1-104256518	cgtgtgctctccgatctATCCTCAGCCCACTTCTCT
Outer_Ch1-104266785	TTGATATCAATGACAGCCAACCTT	Inner_Ch1-104266785	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGTGAAGCTTAGTCATCATGTCCT
Outer_Ch1-104267709	AGTCTACATTCTGGCTGCA	Inner_Ch1-104267709	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCAGTGGCAGTTGATTGCA
Outer_Ch1-104269422	CTTTTCACTGGAAGGGCGA	Inner_Ch1-104269422	cgtgtgctctccgatctCGACCAAGCACTACCACAGT
Outer_Ch1-104280141	CAACATGATTTTTATCCCTCATCCA	Inner_Ch1-104280141	cgtgtgctctccgatctACGGCAGAGTAGTTTGGGAT
Outer_Ch1-104284384	TTTTCTGTACTTCATACCTTTTCCC	Inner_Ch1-104284384	cgtgtgctctccgatctCCCCTTTTGTCCACCCATT
Outer_Ch1-104290534	GCAGTGTGGAGAGAGATAGC	Inner_Ch1-104290534	cgtgtgctctccgatctGCAGTTAGCACAGGGGTTCT
Outer_Ch1-104293471	TGTAGCTGAGGAATTGATGCA	Inner_Ch1-104293471	cgtgtgctctccgatctATCCAGATTCTCTGCGGCC
Outer_Ch2-129143629	TGTCAAGGAGTACAGAAAGGTGG	Inner_Ch2-129143629	cgtgtgctctccgatctTGGAGAAGTTGAGGATCAGCC
Outer_Ch15-5791750	GGTTGACAGGGACATGGATAATTT	Inner_Ch15-5791750	cgtgtgctctccgatctTCAGCTCCCAAGGAACACAC